

Socioeconomic Impacts of Brazil Demand Scenarios of Ethanol via Input Matrix Product with MARIO – 2025 – 2034

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- Keywords

Input Output Matrix; ethanol; Brazil; social and economic impacts (GDP; value added, wages, jobs; imports of gasoline A; CO2 emissions).

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Executive Summary

This Technical Note aims to present considerations on the impacts of socioeconomic scenarios describing the expansion of ethanol demand in Brazil, with the adoption of Input-Output Matrix (IOM) methodology, with the adoption of MARIO tools. For each shock in final demand for ethanol in 2034, ranging from 8.8 billion liters (Low Scenario) to 23.9 billion liters (High Scenario), GDP could increase between R\$64 billion (Low Scenario) and R\$177 billion (High Scenario), corresponding to an increase in GDP of 0.21% (low scenario in 2026) to 1.2% (high scenario in 2034).

Wages could increase between R\$13 billion (Low Scenario) and R\$ 36 billion (High Scenario), representing a growth of 0.12% (Low Scenario) in 2026 to 0.64% (High Scenario) in 2034.

The number of jobs in the country could increase from 630,000 jobs (Low Scenario) to 1.7 million jobs (High Scenario), representing an addition of 0.22% (Low Scenario) in 2026 to 1.13% (High Scenario) in 2034.

To improve these calculations, we can include a hybridization of biofuel manufacturing and petroleum refining, adding additional granularity to the results. Other possible future action would be to insert all these analyses within the full ExioBase database, obtaining a global perspective of incentives to biofuels sector worldwide, including global emissions.

1. Introduction (100-200 words)

This Technical Note connects EPE studies on Ethanol Supply Scenarios and scenarios and demand for Otto-cycle fuels (EPE, 2024c) and EPE Input-Output Matrix (IOM³), adopting MARIO for calculation. By comparing the growth trajectories of the Brazilian Otto-cycle fuel market, we seek to contribute to a better understanding of the possible socioeconomic impacts resulting from the adoption of public policies that affect renewable and fossil fuel sectors, and produce repercussions on other economic sectors, through direct and indirect impacts. This assesses the impact of the Brazilian public policy in Renewable Fuels, known as RenovaBio policy, and its socioeconomic indicators. The multiplier coefficients used in this study are provided by IBGE⁴, and calculated with MARIO. The treatment adopted here is presented to make input-output matrix compatible with the results of the ethanol demand scenarios.

³ The IOM was developed by Leontief (1948), systematized and expanded by Miller and Blair (1985), and used for the analysis of Brazilian national issues by Guilhoto and Sesso (2005), based on national accounts. The Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) presents the results of this matrix approximately every five years.

⁴ See study Socioeconomic Impacts of Ethanol Demand Scenarios via MIP – 2025 – 2034 (EPE, 2024c).

2. Methodology

In terms of Modelling, this paper adopted MARIO (Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input Output), with Python language, Anaconda and Spyder. The modelling approach included analyzing and running the ethanol demand shocks in the database, employing the MARIO tools.

The database used was Input Output tables (Monetary Flows and Technical Coefficients) of Brazil National Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), combined with ExioBase. To use IBGE data, as the test demonstrated, has been more compatible to Brazilian reality than ExioBase, for example. To calculate the ethanol demand shocks, we use the IBGE tables. To evaluate the effects of these ethanol shocks in the GHG emissions for Brazil, we used the ExioBase version 3.5 2022.

The ethanol demand shocks were estimated by EPE Biofuels Teams (EPE, 2024a – “Ethanol Supply Scenarios and Otto Cycle Demand – 2025-2034”) in the horizon of EPE 10-Year Plan – 2025-2034 (EPE, 2024b (PDE 2025-2034)).

Note that it is assumed that BOX scenario is the baseline, and all the scenarios are calculated in comparison to this baseline.

3. Results

The following results were obtained through variations in biofuels and oil products demand, according to EPE (2024c), and multipliers of the 2015 MIP (IBGE, 2016) for GDP, value added, wages, jobs, import of gasoline A and CO2 emissions. All the key IOT calculations were performed using MARIO.

Graph 1 presents the results of the increase in GDP, in the low, medium and high scenarios.

Graph 1 – GDP Growth in Low, Medium and High Scenarios

Source: EPE (2024a), IBGE (2016, 2023a, 2023b).

The increase in GDP results from a shock in total ethanol demand, measured as the difference between the selected scenario and the BOX scenario.

Such increases range from 0.21%⁵ in 2026, to 1.2%⁶ in 2034 (EPE, 2024b). GDP multiplier used was 2.38 (IBGE, 2016).

Graph 2 presents the results for value added, under the low, medium and high scenarios.

Graph 2 – Value added generated in the Low, Medium and High Scenarios

Source: Author's elaboration, based on ExioBase 3.4.9_2024.

⁵ From the combination of low scenario (ethanol demand) with reference macroeconomic scenario (GDP projection).

⁶ From the combination of high scenario (ethanol demand) with the higher macroeconomic scenario (GDP projection).

The Value Added increases resulting from a shock in total ethanol demand, affecting expressively Biofuels production and replacing, hence, decreasing the Oil Refinery and the Oil extraction and production sectors.

Graph 3 presents the results for wages, under the low, medium and high scenarios.

Graph 3 – Wages increase in the Low, Medium and High Scenarios

Source: [EPE](#) (2024a), [IBGE](#) (2016, 2024a, 2024b).

This result consists of an increase in family income when the ethanol revenue shocks.

These impacts described⁷ range from 0.12%⁸ in 2026, to 0.64%⁹ in 2034. Wages multiplier used was 0.43 (IBGE, 2016).

Graph 4 presents the results for employment, under the low, medium and high scenarios.

⁷ As a proportion of total wages projected from 2025 to 2034 (EPE, 2024b).

⁸ From the combination of Low Scenario (ethanol demand) with Reference macroeconomic scenario (GDP projection scenarios).

⁹ From the combination of High Scenario (ethanol demand) with the higher macroeconomic scenario (GDP projection scenario).

Graph 4 – Jobs generated in the Low, Medium and High Scenarios

Source: [EPE](#) (2024a), [IBGE](#) (2016, 2024a, 2024b).

It is observed that in 2034, the low scenario indicates an increase of 630 thousand direct and indirect jobs; in the medium scenario, an increase of 1.17 million and, in the high scenario, an increase of 1.70 million. Note that, as a proportion of the total projected jobs¹⁰ from 2025 to 2034, the impacts vary from 0.22%¹¹ in 2026, to 1.13%¹² in 2034. Employment multiplier used was 20.73 (IBGE, 2016).

Graph 5 presents the results for gasoline imports, under the low, medium and high scenarios.

Graph 5 – Decrease in expenses of Imports of Gasoline A in the Low, Medium and High Scenarios

¹⁰ According to the GDP scenarios (EPE, 2024b).

¹¹ From the combination of Low Scenario (ethanol demand) with Reference macroeconomic scenario (GDP projection).

¹² From the combination of High scenario (ethanol demand) with the high macroeconomic scenario (GDP projection).

Source: [EPE \(2024a\)](#), [IBGE \(2016, 2024a, 2024b\)](#).

The reduction in expenses shown in Chart 5 corresponds to the amount not spent on imports of gasoline A, replaced by fuel ethanol, in the three scenarios. Thus, each year, an ethanol demand shock can contribute to reducing the import bill for gasoline A, which can vary between R\$0.7 billion in 2026 (Low), to R\$ 8.6 billion in 2034 (High). To obtain these values, the multiplier used was 0.21 (IBGE, 2016). In Medium and High scenarios, gasoline A is estimated to be exported.

Graph 6 presents the results for CO2 emissions, under the low, medium and high scenarios.

Graph 6 – CO2 emissions generated in the Low, Medium and High Scenarios

Source: [ExioBase_3.94_2024](#).

Note that the increase in CO2 emissions results from the shock in total ethanol demand, increasing expressively the Biofuels production and replacing, therefore reducing, the Oil Refinery

sector and the Oil extraction and production sector. In summary, the net CO₂ emissions are reduced in the fuels and biofuels sectors.

4. Discussion

The results of each multiplier indicate that shocks in the demand for biofuels (ethanol, in this case) will produce varied impacts on socioeconomic and climatic indicators, while the other conditions remain unchanged, such as the prices of ethanol and prices of gasoline, by simplifying hypothesis.

The results presented here may arise from the consortium of successful actions, such as sector initiatives aimed at improving production factors, with the implementation of public policies.

It is worth noting that the use of biofuels reduces local and global environmental impacts. In its Technical Note "Impact on human health due to the use of biofuels in the Metropolitan Region of São Paulo" (EPE, 2021a), EPE presents different scenarios for the degree of use of biofuels and the reduction of particulate matter emissions, revealing crucial results on the effects on public health.

It is important to highlight that these estimates are not intended to be exact, but rather to indicate, in order of magnitude, the impacts of economic (i.e., GDP, value added, jobs, wages, gasoline imports) and climatic (CO₂ emissions) events. This is because each economic calculation has a margin of error intrinsic to the models adopted.

In addition to the limitations of the input-output matrix model, this study does not include a hybridization of the biofuel manufacturing and petroleum refining and coke plant sectors, which adds an additional layer to the calculation's margin of error. Even so, the model satisfactorily portrays the impacts sought and has been widely used, as it allows macroeconomic estimates of impacts derived from sectoral variations (COSTA & GUILHOTO, 2010; CASTRO et al., 2017; SILVA and FERRARO, 2017).

To improve these calculations, we can include a hybridization of biofuel manufacturing and petroleum refining, adding additional granularity to the results, and, at the same time, putting an additional layer to the calculation's margin of error.

Other possible future action would be to insert all these analyses within the full ExioBase database, obtaining a global perspective of incentives to biofuels sector worldwide.

5. Conclusions and policy insights

This study evaluates socioeconomic impacts of the increase in biofuels demand, adopting different scenarios. The results reveal the socioeconomic impacts of shocks in the final demand for ethanol, resulting from initiatives in the biofuels sector aimed at improving production.

For each shock in final demand for ethanol in 2034, ranging from 8.8 billion liters (Low Scenario) to 23.9 billion liters (High Scenario), GDP could increase between R\$64 billion (Low Scenario) and R\$177 billion (High Scenario), corresponding to an increase in GDP of 0.21% (low scenario in 2026) to 1.2% (high scenario in 2034).

In turn, the variation in wages could increase between R\$13 billion (Low Scenario) and R\$ 36 billion (High Scenario), representing an increase in total wages of 0.12% (Low Scenario in 2026) to 0.64% (High Scenario in 2034).

The number of jobs in the country could increase from 630,000 jobs (Low Scenario) to 1.7 million jobs (High Scenario), representing an addition of 0.22% (Low Scenario in 2026) to 1.13% (High Scenario in 2034).

Regarding the projected totals, note that the highest impacts occur in job creation, then in GDP, and finally wages. Therefore, incentives for the biofuels sector can be very beneficial to the economy.

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